

Selective Electrochemical Thiocyanation of Indoles¹

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Thiocyanation of organic substrates is of interest in view of the possible transformation of thiocyno group into thiols and sulphur containing heterocycles. The claim² that KSCN was present in the saliva of many persons as a result of detoxication of traces of cyanides derived from plant food lend further interest to the present investigation. The thiocyno function had been introduced in organic molecules using a variety of chemical reagents. Thiocyanation of active aromatic systems has been thoroughly reviewed³. Grant and Snyder⁴ reported the thiocyanation of indole using KSCN and bromine to afford 3-thiocyanindole together with 3,3'-indolyldisulphide. There has been renewed interest in the search for novel thiocyanating reagents⁵. Electrochemical thiocyanation of only phenols and some aromatic amines has been reported⁶. More recently⁷ buta-1,3-diene has been electrochemically thiocyanated. Little is known about electrochemical thiocyanation of heterocycles. However, there are reports⁸ on the regio-controlled anodic cyanation of some heterocyclic compounds. In view of the above and in search of alternative methodology, the present paper describes the anodic thiocyanation of some indoles and naphthalene.

Results and Discussion

The anodic thiocyanation of indole (1), 2-phenylindole (2), carbazole (3) and naphthalene (4) was achieved in 47–74 percent yield at constant current using smooth platinum electrodes in acetonitrile containing lithium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte and ammonium thiocyanate as thiocyanating agent. The electrolysis (2F/mol) carried out in an undivided cell afforded selectively the monothiocyno derivatives, viz. 3-thiocyanindole (1a), 2-phenyl-3-thiocyanindole (2a), 3-thiocyanocarbazole (3a) and 1-thiocyanonaphthalene (4a) (Table 1)

The conditions of electrolysis are presented in Table 1. Prior to the actual preparative work the polarisation studies of the substrates were made to ascertain the suitable current density for the electrolysis. Considerable depolarisation is observed in all cases. It has been observed that if the electrolysis of indoles and carbazole is carried out in absence of ammonium thiocyanate, considerable amount of polymer gets deposited on the electrode while in its presence no such polymerisation occurs. In the studied condition of electrolysis, only the monothiocyno derivatives are selectively formed in all cases. The electrochemical thiocyanation seems to be regiocontrolled as the thiocyno function enters at C(3) of the indoles. In case of naphthalene only the 1-thiocyanonaphthalene (4a) is formed exclusively.

TABLE 1—ELECTROLYSIS (2F/mol) OF THE SUBSTRATES (1–4)

Substrate (wt./mmol)	NH ₄ SCN (g)	Current (A) (c.d. A cm ⁻²)	Cell voltage (V)	Temp. (°C)	Product (Yield %)
1 (0.5 g/0.43)	0.8	0.2 (0.026)	8	8	1a (47*)
2 (1.2 g/0.62)	0.5	0.2 (0.026)	5	-8	2a (67)
3 (1.0 g/0.60)	0.5	0.5 (0.067)	6	30	3a (74)
4 (2.0 g/1.5)	1.2	0.2 (0.026)	9	-9	4a (73)

*Isolated on column chromatography (silica gel); eluent: petroleum ether : benzene, 80 : 20 (v/v).

In the ir spectra of 1a–4a, apart from NH absorption of indoles (3450–3350 cm⁻¹), the appearance of a sharp peak around 2160 cm⁻¹ is a positive proof of the presence of SCN function. Moreover, the presence of a band around 760 cm⁻¹ is also indicative⁹ of C(3) substitution of indoles. Pmr spectral data of the products (Table 2) are in agreement with the structures. Further, the proton at C(3) of indoles is reported¹⁰ to give signal at δ 6.2–6.4 ppm. This is absent in the isolated products.

The mass spectra of 1a and 2a as well as the cmr spectrum of 2a are also characteristics of these products. The cyclic voltammetric studies of the thiocyanation with indole as the substrate (Epa, SCN⁻: +800 mV; Epa, indole: +1120 and +1560 mV vs SCE) indicated that first there is in situ generation of thiocyanogen which immediately attacked the organic substrate to afford the thiocyno derivative.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE PRODUCTS (1a–4a)

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Pmr δ
1a ^a	C ₈ H ₆ N ₂ S	77 (76.5)	7.2–8.0 (5H, two m), 8.8 (bs, 1NH)
2a ^b	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ S	175	7.28–7.94 (9H, complex m), 8.74 (bs, 1NH)
3a ^c	C ₁₃ H ₈ N ₂ S	205	7.05–7.9 (m, ArH), 9.04 (bs, 1NH)
4a ^d	C ₁₁ H ₇ NS	52–54 (54)	7.2–7.6, 7.7–8.0 (two complex m, ArH)

^am/z 174. ^bm/z 250. ^cAnalysis: Found: C, 69.55; H, 3.57. Calcd. for: C, 69.64; H, 3.57%. ^dAnalysis: Found: C, 71.28; H, 3.80. Calcd. for: C, 71.35; H, 3.78%.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 Grating spectrometer, pmr spectra on 60 MHz and 100 MHz machines using TMS as reference and cmr spectra on a Brücher NMR spectrometer (90 MHz).

Indole, carbazole and naphthalene (all Fluka), lithium perchlorate, acetonitrile and ammonium thiocyanate (all Merck) were used as such. 2-Phenyl indole (m.p. 188°) was prepared by the reported method¹¹.

Cell assembly: A beaker (250 ml) with a provision to hold a platinum anode and a platinum cathode, a thermometer and magnetic bar, was used as undivided electrolysis cell. The cell was

surrounded with ice-salt mixture to maintain low temperature. The other details are given in Table 1.

Anodic thiocyanation of 2-phenylindole (2). A typical procedure: 2-Phenylindole (1.2 g, 0.62 mmol) dissolved in acetonitrile (100 ml) containing lithium perchlorate (0.2 g) and ammonium thiocyanate (0.5 g), was electrolysed (2F/mol) at constant current. The temperature of the cell was maintained at ~-8° (Table 1). After electrolysis the solvent was distilled off and the residue obtained was stirred with water (50 ml) and then extracted with solvent ether (3×30 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtered. After stripping off the solvent the crude solid product was crystallised from ethanol, (1.04 g, 67%), m.p. 175° (Found: C, 71.35; H, 4.02. C₁₅H₁₀N₂S requires: C, 72.00; H, 4.00%); ν_{max} (KBr) 770, 2160 and 3340 cm⁻¹; pmr δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 7.28–7.94 (9H, complex m), and 8.74 (broad s, 1NH); m/z 250 (M⁺ and base peak), 223, 218, 196, 190, 173, 165 (characteristic for 2-phenylindole)¹² 152, 146, 139, 125, 120, 112, 102, 89, 82, 77, 63 and 53; cmr δ (CDCl₃) 13 absorption peaks at 143.09, 135.47, 130.08, 129.73, 129.55, 128.62, 124.08, 122.1, 119.08, 111.71, 111.60 and 89.34; the peaks were assigned by comparing with the data of 2-phenylindole¹³.

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